

The Translator in Knowledge Management for Innovation – A Semantic Vocation of Value to Industry

Gerhard Goldbeck ^{a,*}, Alexandra Simperler ^a, Nadja Adamovic ^b, Sten-Erik Björling ^c, Vikki Cantrill ^a, Silvia Chiacchiera ^d, Thomas Exner ^e, Irimi Furxhi ^{fg}, David Gao ^h, Mohamedhedi Karray ⁱ, Dimitrios Kiritsis ^j, Jane Lomax ^k, Iseult Lynch ^l, Nicolas Matentzoglu ^m, Michael Noeske ⁿ, Florina Piroi ^b, María Poveda-Villalón ^o, Arkopaul Sarkar ⁱ, Katya Vladislavleva ^p

^a Goldbeck Consulting Limited, UK

^b Technische Universität Wien, Austria

^c Industry Commons Foundation, Sweden

^d STFC UKRI, UK

^e Seven Past Nine GmbH, Germany

^f Transgero Ltd, Ireland

^g University of Limerick, Ireland

^h Nanolayers Research Computing, UK

ⁱ Ecole Nationale D'ingenieurs de Tarbes, France

^j University of Oslo, Norway

^k SciBite Limited, UK

^l University of Birmingham, UK

^m Semanticly, Athens, Greece

ⁿ Fraunhofer IFAM, Bremen, Germany

^o Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Spain

^p Datastories International, Belgium

* Corresponding Author

gerhard@goldbeck-consulting.com

Executive Summary

This white paper has been written by members of the European Union H2020 project OntoCommons and external experts to introduce the concept of a Knowledge Management (KM) Translator - a new and essential function in the within knowledge management. This role bridges the gap between knowledge engineering, semantics, and the needs of materials and manufacturing industries.

Within industries, in which knowledge management plays a vital role or needs to be introduced, it is important to empower individuals to take on the KM Translator role and provide them with the necessary tools and skills to ensure success. This paper discusses the KM Translator role, requirements, and approaches for the successful implementation of knowledge management frameworks in the workplace.

Here, we underline the growing demand to capture and discover knowledge in digital form from a whole data and materials product lifecycle perspective and the challenges faced in identifying client needs, in integrating processes and data, in sharing, and in updating domain-specific knowledge. KM Translators are also expected to offer tailored training strategies and materials to enable addressing these challenges.

We also discuss how other data-science roles intersect, collaborate and support that of the KM Translator, including Data Analysts, Data Custodians, Data Stewards, Data Shepherds, and Knowledge Engineers. Although KM Translators may provide training for employees on the importance of and how to work with new KM-bases systems, they may also need training or up-skilling themselves to be successful. Therefore, this paper provides valuable information and links to third-party courses, books, and other online information sources to facilitate this learning.

This paper presents a comprehensive framework to understand the emerging role of KM Translators, their expertise and project-related responsibilities, and the skills required to excel in this essential role.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	4
2. Industry Needs and Value.....	4
3. KM Translation Processes.....	5
4. Data Science Roles Relevant to KM Translation	7
4.1. Data Analyst.....	7
4.2. Data Custodian.....	8
4.3. Data Steward.....	8
4.4. Data Shepherd	9
4.5. Knowledge Engineer	9
5. Skills and Training	10
5.1. Knowledge Sources for Self-Taught Knowledge-Management Specialists.....	10
5.2. Communication Skills in Knowledge Management	11
5.3. Educating the Next Generation	12
6. Training Needs of the Future.....	12
6.1. Modularisation with Modern Software Solutions.....	12
6.2. Upskilling and Internal Recruitment	13
6.3. Roles of Future Technologies and Approaches.....	13
6.4. A One-Stop Shop for Training Materials.....	14
7. Conclusions and Outlook.....	14
8. Acknowledgements.....	15
9. Disclaimer.....	15
10. Abbreviations and Glossary.....	15
11. References.....	16
12. Appendix A – Data Shepherd Case Study.....	19
13. Appendix B – List of Text Books.....	21
14. Appendix C – List of Blogs, Whitepapers, and Reports.....	21
15. Appendix D – List of MOOCs and Online Training.....	22

1. Introduction

In a recent paper (Goldbeck G. , et al., 2022), some members of the H2020 project OntoCommons¹ and external experts developed a new role, required to support the adoption of semantic knowledge management in industry: the Knowledge Management (KM) Translator for Innovation. For this paper, the authors (members of OntoCommons and external stakeholders) worked to consider how an individual can be empowered to adopt such a role by providing tools to upskill and bring immediate value to a client.

All the authors have experience with a complex range of skills including information and communication technologies (ICT), analytical philosophy, and logic within science/engineering domains. The authors of this paper are scientists and engineers trained in semantics, ontologies, and knowledge management with expertise in specific science and engineering domains. As active educators, they also advise how education organisations can enthuse the next generation to be interested in and take up KM Translator roles.

As an outcome of the collaboration between these authors, we characterise here the KM Translator role. That is, a KM Translator must have a thorough understanding of knowledge engineering and the willingness to support data sharing among materials and manufacturing companies and communities. They need to be able to map science and engineering aspects to a wide range of semantic technologies and knowledge/data.

2. Industry Needs and Value

Knowledge management requirements in industry are numerous and continuously evolving. In the age of digital transformations, interconnection and interoperability between different domains are sought after, leading to a strong increase in the exploration and adoption of semantic data management.

The underlying need has been discussed in many areas of manufacturing. For example, Feng et al. (Feng, Bernstein, Hedberg Jr., & Barnard Feeney, 2017) identified the increasing variety and complexity of product lifecycle applications as a driver for change in manufacturing industries. Hence, manufacturers face a growing need for "*capturing knowledge in the digital form in design, process planning, production, and inspection*" and, because of new societal priorities and legislation, intentional and unintentional use, end of life and recyclability addressing safety, sustainability, and circularity. Although progress in smart manufacturing is hampered by the "*lack of mechanisms for integrating, sharing, and updating domain-specific knowledge*" and by missing cross-domain interoperability and standards, targeted knowledge management tasks and workflows in enterprises are being established.

Wang et al. (Wang & Peng, 2023) highlight that data models and knowledge management for digital twins and cyber-physical systems are central to intelligent business decisions, which themselves are based on five stages; cognition, planning, pilot, promotion and support, and institutionalization. Enterprise knowledge management can be a critical challenge for managers and achieving intelligent

¹ <https://www.ontocommons.eu/>; <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/958371>

business decisions requires a lot more than data analysis. The role of KM Translator is to integrate this wider context and hence KM Translators will require awareness and training in these fields, as well as to support knowledge managers to bring about “client adoption including training” as highlighted by Goldbeck et al. (Goldbeck G. , et al., 2022)

3. KM Translation Processes

Consultants and trainers often work together with clients on challenging problems and innovative ideas that requires them to research and assimilate new information and find new solutions; a process, we will refer to here as KM translation. The methods and processes behind this work are often undocumented so there is no comprehensive analysis or best practice of the steps to implementation. However, we can still describe the important steps in a general way and show how KM Translators can bring structure into the process and define high-quality, standardised approaches.

The KM translation processes range from gaining a client’s attention and confidence to understanding the innovation challenges, regardless of whether the KM Translator role is filled by persons inside or external to the organisation. Initially, the KM Translator establishes with the client how KM can best be utilised to tackle the innovation challenge and poses questions to gain a complete understanding of the clients’ expectations and needs. The KM Translator needs to know what existing architecture there is and what existing workflows the organisation has in place. Then, semantics and ontologies can be brought in where they are of most benefit. The KM Translator may well provide case studies to show to the clients and manage their expectations. A proof-of-concept study may be advisable, whereby a paid for, short termed project (ranging from a couple of days to a couple of weeks, depending on the complexity of the innovation challenge and client entity) can give the customer a clear view on the capabilities and limitations of adopting a solution. This can be a new system, a new set of data, new people, etc.

KM Translators help clients to bridge the knowledge gap between their ideas and a practical implementation of actions. As highlighted by Schöffner (Schöffner, 2002) the concept of “knowledge” is very relevant to translation processes and the process/understanding of “translation” evolves continuously. Translation involves cognitive processes, like parsing information and taking decisions. Consequently, KM Translators must understand the context and meaning of the knowledge to be managed. Furthermore, KM need to collaboratively support clients in pursuing best practices for KM implementation, and have a particular role in supporting training for their clients with a focus on the respective knowledge and its management. (Yew Wong, 2005)

Typically, KM is highly collaborative. (Wang & Peng, 2023) Moreover, knowledge comprises both the information and its context, so KM clients will expect Translators to understand the context in which knowledge is to be applied and exchanged. A holistic KM approach relies on the Translators to master all the relevant knowledge aspects, e.g., considering scientific-actual, social-relational, and cognitive-mental knowledge domains. (Nakamori, 2020)

To enhance the procedural integration of KM Translation in industrial, established processes (e.g., innovation management, and trouble-shooting), a step-wise strategical approach is recommended. Based on the target and purpose of the respective knowledge-bearing industrial process, the general

strategy should involve the KM Translator becoming acquainted with all the processes and roles involved. A more customer-specific part of the strategy is to have contact with everyone responsible for these processes and the role holders.

Alignment of KM Translation with industrial processes requiring domain specific training

In the following, we outline steps to help KM Translators identify industrial applications that use KM or would profit from a knowledge management approach. The importance of each step will depend on the specific application and whether any KM-based reasoning already exists.

Step 1: Identify industrially relevant processes that already involve some sort of KM

Step 2: Develop networks with persons holding relevant roles (see Chapter 4) in the industrial processes

Step 3: With the above network, identify the needs of the actors in industrial processes involving KM

Step 4: With the above network, develop beneficial strategies to establish KM Translation.

For example, an industrially relevant process for which knowledge management can improve intelligent and cross-disciplinary decision making is failure analysis. Failure analysis informs decisions in different fields, including improvements in the development of materials, the choice of materials, design, production, and operational processes. Moreover, failure analysis provides knowledge that can be applied in quality control, help prevent failures and facilitate innovation. The contribution of KM hence will integrate data and knowledge from these disciplines such that documenting of failures can assist different areas of a business. In this way, knowledge-driven innovation can help industry to determine "*the optimal combination of material, design, production and component properties in view of the relative cost*". A good starting point and basis for the work of KM Translators active in materials design and production is the guideline VDI 3822 "Failure analysis – Fundamentals and performance of failure analysis".² The document covers fundamentals and terminology, as well as how failure analyses are performed and documented. From a procedural point of view, KM Translators benefit from understanding how their stakeholders act to assess and record observed failures.

The guideline document recommends having a person in charge of performing a failure analysis; a role inextricably linked with responsibility and performance criteria because failure analysis is qualitative and objective. A suggested workflow includes failure description, recording failure history, rising failure hypothesis (hypotheses), instrumental analyses, detecting causes of failure, performing actions to correct failure, and reporting.

The person in charge may profit from support by a KM Translator to target and direct time-consuming analyses, outline instrumental approaches to gather missing data, and develop scientific methods to assess findings. In this way, KM Translators help shape the business and the industrial cases to identify missing data. [see also (Klein, et al., 2021)]

In general, the KM Translator should have the ability to increase and use already existing and developed knowledge resources, practices, and methodologies, and may interact with an organisations' existing knowledge bases and networks.

² <https://www.vdi.de/en/home/vdi-standards/details/vdi-3822-failure-analysis-fundamentals-and-performance-of-failure-analysis-1>

So far, we note that KM Translators

- will suggest, establish, and demonstrate mechanisms for integrating, sharing, and updating domain-specific knowledge;
- may be expected to provide guidance to clients whose enterprises (though data-ready) may not be KM-ready;
- need to train themselves utilising suitable domain resources and in particular standard procedures and guidelines in the area of the industrial case as well as support client training in KM to ensure successful adoption.

We will now

- highlight that applications of KM include ontology development and domain-specific tasks, e.g., in manufacturing some lifecycle assessment, quality-problem traceability, and product-design improvement. (Feng, Bernstein, Hedberg Jr., & Barnard Feeney, 2017)
- recommend proactively developing training strategies and materials.

4. Data Science Roles Relevant to KM Translation

If a company is already data-aware and has persons working in data related roles, the KM Translator will want to quickly onboard and work with them. These persons know the readiness level of a company, can provide recommendation regarding the data and processes that would most benefit from KM, and give insight into the constraints under which the KM Translator has to work. Of course, any proposed solutions must integrate with current workflows/processes and work within constraints such as must-use components and security requirements. Some of the pertinent roles and tasks to identify within the company or also outside for this stage-setting and for providing more knowledge or alternative approaches are discussed below. We note that depending on context, different roles will be prominent. For example, Data Stewards / Data Shepherds are typically found in the FAIR community, while Knowledge Engineers tend emerge from the information sciences. Also, the list below is of course by no means complete in terms of job titles, as there are e.g., Data Managers and Knowledge Managers.

4.1. Data Analyst

Data Analysts frequently work with or in large organisations that have large amounts of disperse data that could be combined to gain knowledge. Typically, Data analysts will combine and track data, and produce dashboards to make knowledge management more user friendly. Often, organisations have a budget for data governance. (Alexandru, et al., 2023) Therefore, we need to identify what problems a KM Translator can solve that are not already solved by data analysts.

Broadly speaking, Data Analysts want to ‘consume’ large volumes of data. They may hence prefer data lakes, whereby all data resides in a centralised repository. However, they also require clean and clear data annotations, and that data be tracked as it flows through an enterprise, such that it is still trusted once it enters the data lake. Here ontologies can help because they can be used to “tag” whether the data stem from (in-house) materials properties databases or are live data from characterisation, materials modelling, experiments, or sensors. Semantic technologies are hence useful to Data Analysts because they help locating the required data and improve management of models.

The KM Translator works towards excellent data quality and observability, while supporting privacy and security. To this end, organisations may be offered frameworks and governance structures to allow for effective data searches and controlled access. Tangible improvements (on knowledge sharing, innovation, discovery) are expected and organisations need to understand the net gain over time. In other words, any change must be associated with a positive cost-benefit analysis and it should be possible to demonstrate the impacts on specific applications/tasks.

Data Analysts are key to achieving these tangible benefits, for example by implementing easier integration of and specific tooling for semantically annotated data. The latter processes in turn contribute to reducing data errors. Also, once a new KM solution is in place, the Data Analyst will be able to support the KM Translator in validating it.

The Data Analyst will also greatly benefit from the roles discussed below (custodian, steward, etc.) and also be able to feed-back requirements that the custodian, shepherd, steward, etc., should include in their processes.

4.2. Data Custodian

Data Custodians are responsible for the safe and secure storage, maintenance, and retrieval of data. They implement and maintain data infrastructure, databases, and data systems, ensuring their availability and security. (Hevner, March, Park, & Ram, 2014) Data Custodians often collaborate closely with Data Shepherds to ensure that data management processes adhere to governance policies and procedures. (Wang, Storey, & Firth, 2019) Typically, the KM Translator would consult with the Data Custodian to ensure that all data is managed in accordance with relevant policies.

4.3. Data Steward

Data Stewards play a crucial role in ensuring data quality and usability. They act as subject-matter experts in specific data domains or business areas. (Wang, Storey, & Firth, 2019) Data Stewards collaborate with Data Shepherds and Data Custodians to define and enforce data standards, resolve data-related issues, and promote data literacy within an organisation. (Hevner, March, Park, & Ram, 2014) They are responsible for data profiling, metadata management, data documentation, and supporting the implementation of the FAIR principles³ (Wilkinson & al., 2016), and thus, making data more accessible and understandable for users. (Kamilaris, Fonts, & Prenafeta-Boldú, 2019) It is

³ FAIR stands for: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

anticipated that Data Stewards and KM Translators would collaborate closely to ensure that all data is well-managed throughout their lifecycle and remains accessible to all users.

4.4. Data Shepherd

The Data Shepherd (Papadiamantis, et al., 2020) was developed independently but has a large overlap with KM Translators but is more located in the setting of large (publicly funded) research projects in need of harmonising knowledge sharing between many partners. It is a role that is related to, but goes beyond, that of the Data Steward to oversee the whole data lifecycle. Their responsibilities include overseeing data management, handling, and ensuring data quality. Data Shepherds may have a combination of experimental, computational, and technical experience. Their tasks involve leading data quality control and evaluation of FAIR principles. Additionally, Data Shepherds are responsible for continuously optimizing data workflows and implementing technical advancements to facilitate data curation, annotation, harmonisation, and cleansing. An Example of Data Shepherding can be found in Appendix A.

Data Shepherds improve data management by overseeing data creation and ensuring data completeness and quality. By implementing data-governance practices, customised to a consortium or even individual partners but still providing harmonised and interoperable data, they contribute to reliable and trustworthy data assets, which are crucial for informed decision-making and strategic planning.

Data Shepherds, like KM Translators, must have excellent communication skills to effectively resolve any misconceptions or miscommunication. They must bridge the gap between technical experts and non-technical stakeholders, effectively translating knowledge into clear and simple language, facilitating effective communication, and fostering better collaboration across different teams and departments. The Data Shepherd also needs a comprehensive understanding of data in different contexts. This understanding allows them to identify data-driven opportunities that can benefit the industry.

4.5. Knowledge Engineer

According to Technopedia (Rouse, 2019), "*a knowledge engineer is a professional engaged in the science of building advanced logic into computer systems in order to try to simulate human decision-making and high-level cognitive tasks.*" Knowledge Engineers build knowledge-based system (KBS), i.e., computer models with problem-solving capabilities comparable to a domain expert. (Studer, Benjamins, & Fensel, 1998) Role responsibilities include assessment, elicitation, structure, and validation. (Campana, 2022) There is a strong overlap between the tasks currently carried out by Knowledge Engineers and the role of the KM Translator. Successful technical knowledge engineering requires detailed analysis of the problem, which will be supported by a KM Translator, e.g., by conducting interviews, and decision on which data is needed and where it will come from. The wider remit of the KM Translator should provide more context and business benefit analysis on which the Knowledge Engineer can build. As such the KM Translator and Knowledge Engineer, respectively, fulfil the consulting/business-oriented and technical/implementation-oriented roles. The Knowledge Engineer must build a technology stack for the KBS able to address the problem requirements.

Finally, the Knowledge Engineer is responsible for verification and validation of the final knowledge asset so a user can be assured that a KBS works well and can be trusted.

5. Skills and Training

5.1. Knowledge Sources for Self-Taught Knowledge-Management Specialists

Valuable sources of information for KM are textbooks, a selection of which are listed in Appendix B, and blogs. Of particular interest is a blog by Henriette Harmse,⁴ who says “*The problem is that the underlying theory and plethora of Semantic Web tools present software developers with a steep learning curve.*” These concerns are also relevant to KM Translators. Chris Mungall gives advice and tips from real-life experiences on his “Monkeying around with OWL” blog aimed at ontology developers of all abilities, and shares information about how challenges were mastered. Similarly, KM Translators could profit from their own database of problems and frequently asked questions to try and resolve or search for commonly encountered issues. Some companies, such as SciBite⁵, Stardog⁶, Ontotext⁷ and CambridgeSemantics⁸ also offer blogs, whitepapers, and knowledge/publication hubs that provide information about the latest developments in KM. (see Appendix C)

Another interactive, training source are massive open online courses (MOOCs). Providers worldwide offer online courses and trainees can participate from home at a time convenient to them. Many such courses are free, although some are paid for, and some providers offer certificates for completing a course. Some providers that cover KM are listed in Appendix C. In addition, KM requires knowledge about FAIR data and for this the GO FAIR resources⁹, RDA FAIR¹⁰, FAIRsFAIR¹¹, ELIXIR FAIRCOOKBOOK¹² and RDMkit¹³, and WorldFAIR¹⁴ are a good starting point.

The OBO Academy¹⁵ is a community resource that covers bio/biomedical sectors and the Open Biological and Biomedical Ontology (OBO) Foundry¹⁶ is the umbrella organisation, which was set up to foster shared principles. Here, ontologies are expected to be interoperable and scientifically accurate. The OBO academy is for beginners and experts alike. Semantics and ontologies form part of cutting-edge developments for this active community. The academy hosts tutorials, how-to guides, reference guides, and explanations. Users are invited to interact by reporting issues,

⁴ <https://henrietteharmse.com/>

⁵ <https://scibite.com/>

⁶ <https://www.stardog.com/>

⁷ <https://www.ontotext.com/>

⁸ <https://cambridgesemantics.com/>

⁹ <https://www.go-fair.org/resources/>

¹⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/fair>

¹¹ <https://www.fairsfair.eu/>

¹² <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/>

¹³ <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>

¹⁴ <https://worldfair-project.eu/>

¹⁵ <https://oboacademy.github.io/obook/>

¹⁶ <http://obofoundry.org/>

suggesting new lessons, and writing content. The OBO academy grew over time from providing training for Critical Path Institute¹⁷ members, to training to third parties and, now, considering user requests. The first users, from the Critical Path Institute, were ontology curators, engineers, developers, and contributors, now, users may dip in to short tutorials or spend several hours learning new skills.

The OntoCommons project also hosts several resources, such as the OntoCommons Eco System (OCES). (d'Aquin, 2021) This system provides an integrated, harmonised framework of top- and middle-level ontologies (TLOs and MLOs), as well as related, widely agreed domain ontologies to support a pluralistic approach, which makes it more easily adaptable to end-user requirements.

A report by Slaughter & Otten (Slaughter & Otten, 2022) may be useful for KM Translators to check which well-supported ontologies are used in nanotechnologies, advanced materials, biotechnology, and advanced manufacturing and processing (NMBP) application domains. Similarly, a report by Le Franc (Le Franc, 2022) can be used to check for existing domain ontologies, rather than developing new ones. Skjæveland et al. (Skjæveland, Slaughter, & Kindermann, 2022) lists useful software systems. A review of domain interoperability is being developed within OntoCommons, designed for developers (at domain level) of ontologies and tools/components that use them. The review addresses all aspects of interoperability with a particular focus on semantic data interoperability. It includes pointers to existing terminologies and classifications of interoperability types, recommendations, and a list of helpful tools. Poveda-Villalón and colleagues have proposed the Linked Open Terms (LOT) Methodology, (Poveda-Villalón, Fernández-Izquierdo, Fernández-López, & García-Castro, 2022) an overall, lightweight method to build ontologies based on existing systems and oriented to semantic web developments and technologies. The method includes lessons learnt from more than 20 years' experience in ontological engineering and its application to 18 projects.

5.2. Communication Skills in Knowledge Management

KM translation involves intra- and inter-organisational stakeholders in a dynamic, interactive, and interdisciplinary process. The target is to reach a consensus on the exchange of jointly ontologised knowledge. In our experience, agreeing an exchange of data is considerably faster than agreeing to exchange knowledge-based assets. Thus, KM Translators, must operate on a social, intersubjective level and co-operate with all relevant stakeholders. Typically, they will team up to interact with customers and also with other experts in materials modelling or in materials characterisation. The KM Translator can bring in ontology-based translation and reveal the benefits of documenting and organising newly generated knowledge resulting from a jointly established approach within a team. Often, whilst collaboratively working on one idea, additional projects to manage disperse, existing intra- and inter-organisational knowledge are also identified within an organisation.

¹⁷ <https://c-path.org/>

5.3. Educating the Next Generation

Several universities offer courses to learn about KM, for example, the University of Manchester offers tutorials around ontology engineering.¹⁸

At TU Vienna, computer science students of the Data Science master curricula, have to study specific methods for data science, like data collection, data cleaning data, data visualization and interpretation, apply machine learning algorithms for prediction, use semantic methods for data description, etc. The university's Data Science MSc¹⁹ therefore, offers lectures in Machine Learning, statistics, high-performance computing, data analysis, and domain-specific data science. Guest lecturers in chemistry, physics, earth sciences and social sciences introduce students to contemporary data problems. The students then complete internships naturally cross over to different data domains and learn by doing how to engage collaboratively and solve real problems. TU Vienna also extended the data management education to cover data life cycles, FAIR principles, data preservation, versioning, and citation.

Another example is the STI Innsbruck²⁰ where 50% of computer science students leave for industry with a BSc. Many become software developers in the manufacturing sector and telecommunication is an often-pursued career path. Engagement with data semantics happens during the MSc courses during which students take lectures and practical training on knowledge graphs, semantic web, and smart data during a semester. The educators encourage cross-domain work for students involved in projects that show them the value of semantics. Guest speakers, who have a demonstrator case with OntoCommons, also show students the impact semantics/ontology has in a real industrial setting.

The examples given above are centred on Computer Science, which traditionally was seen as provider of tools to knowledge managers and engineers. However, as the technological complexity in manufacturing increases, domain specific knowledge for the correct development and use of such tools is now a necessity. That is, after completing their studies, students may understand the principles of KM but lack experience in NMBP domains. Internships and joint academia-industry PhD programmes may alleviate these concerns, perhaps by profiting from a Marie Skłodowska Curie Action.²¹ Also, communications skills development in a multi-disciplinary, business-technical setting needs to be further strengthened.

6. Training Needs of the Future

6.1. Modularisation with Modern Software Solutions

Regardless of what strategy an organisation implements for its knowledge management processes, it is important to think in terms of flexibility and usability regarding end-users. You cannot use resources you cannot find, or effectively use knowledge resources if they are too fragmented or do not fit to other components already used in an organisation. Structural modularisation of knowledge resources also allows for effective support for the flow certification tests → skills gap analysis

¹⁸ <http://owl.cs.manchester.ac.uk/about/ontology-engineering/>

¹⁹ <https://informatics.tuwien.ac.at/master/data-science/>

²⁰ <https://www.sti-innsbruck.at/teaching/curriculum>

²¹ <https://marie-sklodowska-curie-actions.ec.europa.eu/>

→ customised training design → accurate statistics and reporting → future training needs estimation. (Björling, Baglee, Galar, Singh, & Kumar, 2013) (Björling & Kumar, 2009) (Björling S.-E. , 2001)

A training module can contain several resources for a given topic, widening tool exposure to allow learners to adapt the learning process according to their own needs and challenges. For example, the mainframe could show a presentation that is linked to other content depending on training needs, such as documents, links to external sources, or links to associated expertise.

Modular training and learning resources are vital when implementing qualified and advanced training in private and public sector organisations and businesses that mostly do not have time to relieve their qualified staff to participate in university courses or long-term training programmes. Companies often need direct access to training solutions or links to external expertise.

6.2. Upskilling and Internal Recruitment

Knowledge/skill levels are and will increase in importance for organisations that are working with ever-more fragmented asset fleets and complex processes. Knowing your staff's knowledge and skill level is essential not only for day-to-day business but becomes increasingly critical with increased competition and resource scarcity. In many cases, the best candidate for a job might be an employee with a highly specialised skills profile – but the organisation is unaware of their existence.

In the context of interaction with external/internal KM Translators, two processes can support practical knowledge translation efforts – internal certification tests and knowledge gap analysis (ILO approach). (ILO, 2007)

Certification processes based on effective mapping between certification elements with relevant knowledge/practices learning modules can lower the overall costs and time used to bring up staff to higher usable skills and knowledge levels by supporting the creation of individual learning packages. In the context of KM translation, additional skills can facilitate interactions with external specialists.

Certification tests can also be used to evaluate internal knowledge inventory. Such systems are vital for organisations to more accurately delegate staff with relevant knowledge levels to efforts, such as KM translation or ontology development.

Finally, KM Translators must be aware of and follow the growing regulatory framework regarding data as well as Artificial Intelligence (AI). In addition to GDPR, the European Union (EU) has or is proposing various “Acts” regarding data²², AI²³, and interoperability²⁴. With regards to AI frameworks are being developed to enable trust, ensure explainability, expose biases, and so on.

6.3. Roles of Future Technologies and Approaches

Currently, the technical developments in AI, deep learning and big data are massive. Approaches for managing data and resources include using knowledge graphs and large language models (LLM). Also, there are interoperability challenges for different end-user contexts, mainly arising from the

²² <https://www.eu-data-act.com/>

²³ [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/698792/EPRS_BRI\(2021\)698792_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/698792/EPRS_BRI(2021)698792_EN.pdf)

²⁴ https://commission.europa.eu/publications/interoperable-europe-act-proposal_en

need to handle data and information in legacy systems simultaneously. It is not always possible or profitable to adapt/transfer some legacy systems to new technologies. Thus, any systems developed must support adaptable interoperability strategies to be able to handle modern and legacy data.

In the context of KM and IT-based learning systems, LLMs will continue to grow in importance due to their potential to assist users, by natural language interaction, to design appropriate solutions or instruct on the use of KM tools. This technology will be vital in the context of creating meta systems integrating different maturity levels of knowledge resource repositories.

6.4. A One-Stop Shop for Training Materials

There is a danger that all training materials developed in private are only used by a select group. Readily available, well-indexed, open training materials can help combat challenges, such as complex working environments, increased complexity of innovation challenges, reduced or limited availability of specialised staff, and fragmented work processes. Training repositories must allow search mechanisms and terms that can be understood by interested persons, combined with effective end-user interfaces. Search mechanisms and terminology approaches should be common across an organisation - databases for specialists and researchers, research data, statistics and geocoded attribute data are examples and could be disseminated through effective market platforms, such as DOME 4.0.

The main project partners have created an international Alliance called KGA (International Semantic and FAIR Knowledge Graph Alliance) that will continue the work on building the Knowledge Translation role by providing training and building training materials through a dedicated service called the KGA Academy. The Academy also aims to establish collaborations with universities to develop curricula for educating cross-domain experts in the use and development of Semantic Knowledge Graphs Technologies.

7. Conclusions and Outlook

The proposed new role of Knowledge Management Translator for Innovation requires a wide range of skills relating to data management, semantic modelling, knowledge engineering, and of course the ability to identify how these technologies can be utilised to solve business problems. As industry need, e.g., regarding “integrating, sharing, and updating domain-specific knowledge” (Feng, Bernstein, Hedberg Jr., & Barnard Feeney, 2017) is sharply increasing, solutions based on skilled KM Translation will be more and more sought after.

Business acumen, as well as strong communication skills, enable the KM Translator to fully understand stakeholders’ needs and the translation project scope through consensus of stakeholder opinion. KM Translators are expected to have expertise in both the initial and final knowledge-based translation domains. Their translation activities should reflect their mastery of the knowledge-based translation process and their insights into industrial process workflows that involve KM activities. KM Translators will be involved in shaping both the business and industrial cases (Klein, et al., 2021) to

identify missing data directed by a Translator in materials characterisation and/or in materials modelling.

In order to meet these challenges, KM Translators will need to work with a range of experts such as Data Analysts and Knowledge Engineers. A range of such roles have been discussed in this paper, though it will by no means be complete. Furthermore, KM Translators will need to continuously advance their skills, expertise, and competency in both ontology-based knowledge management processes and in relevant business areas. KM Translators may also profit from communication and interpersonal skills training.

To enable KM Translators to acquire and improve their skills, a wide range of resources are required. We have laid out the key areas and gathered some of the resources available as well as discussed requirements and propose ways to educate the next generation.

We recommend further development of training strategies and materials that demonstrate end-to-end examples from both the Translator and industrial client perspective and call for up-skilling with a focus on exchange between semantic technologies experts and materials and manufacturing domain challenges.

8. Acknowledgements

This study has received financial support from the EU H2020 project OntoCommons GA n. 958371.

9. Disclaimer

All statements of fact, opinion, or analysis expressed in the report are those of the authors. The information used and statements of fact made are not guarantees, warranties or representations as to their completeness or accuracy. The authors assume no liability for any short-term or long-term decision made by any reader based on suggestions included in this report. In many cases, the opinion expressed in the reports is the authors' current opinion based on prevailing trends and is subject to change. The authors are not endorsing any mentioned organisations or companies or function as their broker/dealer. Links are provided for the sole purpose of underlining the thoroughness of their research.

10. Abbreviations and Glossary

AI - Artificial Intelligence

EU – European Union

FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable

ICT - Information and communications technology

ILO – International Labour Organization

KGA - International Semantic and FAIR Knowledge Graph Alliance)

KM – Knowledge Management: the collection of methods relating to creating, sharing, using and managing the knowledge and information of an organization. It refers to a multidisciplinary approach to achieve organisational objectives by making the best use of knowledge.
[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Knowledge_management#:~:text=Knowledge%20management%20\(KM\)%20is%20the,the%20best%20use%20of%20knowledge](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Knowledge_management#:~:text=Knowledge%20management%20(KM)%20is%20the,the%20best%20use%20of%20knowledge) .

LLM - large language models

MOOC - Massive Open Online Course

NEP - nano-enabled product

NM – nano material

NMBP - Nanotechnologies, Advanced Materials, Biotechnology and Advanced Manufacturing and Processing.

OCES - OntoCommons Eco System (d'Aquin, 2021)

SSbD - Safe and Sustainable by Design

11. References

- Alexandru, R., McKay, P., Koetzle, L., Maheshwari, S., Goetz, M., Say, M., & Starks, D. (2023, Sept 25). *The Forrester Wave™: Data Governance Solutions, Q3 2023*. Retrieved from Collibra: <https://www.collibra.com/us/en/resources/collibra-recognized-as-a-leader-in-the-forrester-wave-data-governance-solutions-q-3-2023>
- Björling, S. E., & Kumar, U. (2009). ICT concepts for managing future challenges in E-maintenance. . *International Congress on Condition Monitoring and Diagnostic Engineering Management*. San Sebastian, Spain: Fundaci n Tekniker.
- Björling, S.-E. (2001, April 16). *Meeting future demands for hydro training*. Retrieved from Waterpower Magazine: <https://www.waterpowermagazine.com/features/featuremeeting-future-demands-for-hydro-training/>
- Björling, S.-E., Baglee, D., Galar, D., Singh, S., & Kumar, U. (2013, July 22). *Maintenance knowledge management with fusion of CMMS and CM*. Retrieved from International Conference on Data Mining, Las Vegas, Nevada, USA: <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1001339/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- Campana, N. (2022, Sep 23). *What does a Knowledge Engineer do?* Retrieved from Freelancer Map: <https://www.freelancermap.com/blog/what-does-knowledge-engineer-do/>
- d'Aquin, M. (2021, June 7). *OntoCommons D4.1 - Ontology Ecosystem Specification*. Retrieved from Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6504633>
- Del Secco, B., Trabucco, S., Ravegnani, F., Koivisto, A., Zanoni, I., Blosi, M., . . . Belosi, F. (2022). Particles Emission from an Industrial Spray Coating Process Using Nano-Materials. . *Nanomaterials* 12, 313.

- Feng, S., Bernstein, W., Hedberg Jr., T., & Barnard Feeney, A. (2017). Toward Knowledge Management for Smart Manufacturing . *J. Comput. Inf. Sci. Eng.* 17(3), 031016.
- Furxhi, I. (2022). Health and environmental safety of nanomaterials: O Data, Where Art Thou? *NanoImpact* 25, 100378.
- Furxhi, I., Arvanitis, A., Murphy, F., Costa, A., & Blosi, M. (2021). Data Shepherding in Nanotechnology. The Initiation. *Nanomaterials* 11(6), 1520.
- Furxhi, I., Koivisto, A., Murphy, F., Trabucco, S., Del Secco, B., & Arvanitis, A. (2021). Data Shepherding in Nanotechnology. The Exposure Field Campaign Template. *Nanomaterials* 11, 1818.
- Furxhi, I., Perucca, M., Blosi, M., Lopez de Ipiña, J., Oliveira, J., Murphy, F., & Costa, A. L. (2022). ASINA Project: Towards a Methodological Data-Driven Sustainable and Safe-by-Design Approach for the Development of Nanomaterials. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology* 9, 805096.
- Furxhi, I., Varesano, A., Salman, H., Mirzaei, M., Battistello, V., Tomasoni, I., & Blosi, M. (2021). Data Shepherding in Nanotechnology: An Antimicrobial Functionality Data Capture Template. *Coatings* 11, 1486.
- Goldbeck, G., Simperler, A., Bull, L. G., Karray, M., Kharlamov, E., Kiritsis, D., . . . Noeske, M. P. (2022). The Translator in Knowledge Management for Innovation – towards Industry Commons. *Zenodo*.
- Goldbeck, G., Simperler, A., Bull, L., Gao, D., Ghedini, E., Karray, M., . . . Waaler, A. (2022, Sep 1). *The Translator in Knowledge Management for Innovation – towards Industry Commons*. Retrieved from Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7041697>
- Hevner, A. ., March, S. T., Park, J., & Ram, S. (2014). Design science in information systems research. *MIS Quarterly* 28 (1), 75-105.
- ILO. (2007, July). *Rights, Labour Migration and Development: The ILO approach*. Retrieved from International Labour Office Geneva: https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_protect/---protrav/---migrant/documents/briefingnote/wcms_203885.pdf
- Kamilaris, A., Fonts, A., & Prenafeta-Boldú, F. X. (2019). A review on the practice of big data analysis in agriculture. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 162, 529-443.
- Klein, P., Konchakova, N., Hristova-Bogaerds, D. G., Noeske, M., Simperler, A., Goldbeck, G., & Höche, D. (2021, April 30). *Translation in Materials Modelling – Process and Progress*. Retrieved from Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/record/4729918>
- Koivisto, A. J., Spinazzè, A., Verdonck, F., Borghi, F., Löndahl, J., Koponen, I. K., . . . Furxhi, I. (2021). Assessment of exposure determinants and exposure levels by using stationary concentration measurements and a probabilistic near-field/far-field exposure model. *Open Res Europe* 1, 71.
- Le Franc, Y. (2022, March 9). *OntoCommons D3.2 - Report on existing domain ontologies*. Retrieved from Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6504553>
- Mirzaei, M., Furxhi, I., Murphy, F., & Mullins, M. (2021). A Supervised Machine-Learning Prediction of Textile’s Antimicrobial Capacity Coated with Nanomaterials. *Coatings* 11, 1532.

- Mirzaei, M., Furxhi, I., Murphy, F., & Mullins, M. (2021). A Machine Learning Tool to Predict the Antibacterial Capacity of Nanoparticles. *Nanomaterials* 11, 1774.
- Nakamori, Y. (2020). Fusing Systems Thinking with Knowledge Management. *J. Syst. Sci. Syst. Eng.* 29, 291–305.
- Papadiamantis, A. G., Klaessig, F. C., Exner, T. E., Hofer, S., Hofstaetter, N., Himly, M., . . . Lynch, I. (2020). Metadata Stewardship in Nanosafety Research: Community-Driven Organisation of Metadata Schemas to Support FAIR Nanoscience Data. *Nanomaterials* 10, 2033.
- Poveda-Villalón, M., Fernández-Izquierdo, A., Fernández-López, M., & García-Castro, R. (2022). LOT: An industrial oriented ontology engineering framework. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence* 111, 104755.
- Rouse, M. (2019, Feb 5). *What Does Knowledge Engineer Mean?* Retrieved from Technopedia: <https://www.techopedia.com/definition/7966/knowledge-engineer>
- Schäffner, C. (2002). Knowledge Systems and Translation. (Text, Translation, Computational Processing 7). *HERMES - Journal of Language and Communication in Business*, 20, 221–234.
- Skjæveland, M. G., Slaughter, L. A., & Kindermann, C. (2022, April 20). *OntoCommons D4.3 - Report on Landscape Analysis of Ontology Engineering Tools*. Retrieved from Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6504670>
- Slaughter, L. A., & Otten, J. (2022, Jan 12). *OntoCommons D2.2 - TLO/MLO Landscape Analysis Report*. Retrieved from Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6504440>
- Studer, R., Benjamins, V., & Fensel, D. (1998). Knowledge engineering: Principles and methods. *Data & Knowledge Engineering* 25 (1-2), 161-197.
- Wang, H., & Peng, G. (2023). The Merging of Knowledge Management and New Information Technologies. . In H. Wang, & G. Peng, *Collaborative Knowledge Management Through Product Lifecycle*. (pp. 229–283). Singapore: Springer.
- Wang, R. Y., Storey, V. C., & Firth, C. P. (2019). A framework for analysis of data quality research. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* 7(4), 623-640.
- Wilkinson, M., & al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data* 3, 160018.
- Yew Wong, K. (2005). Critical success factors for implementing knowledge management in small and medium enterprises. *Industrial Management & Data Systems* 105, 261-279.

12. Appendix A – Data Shepherd Case Study

One example, in which the shepherd role was implemented is the ASINA²⁵ project. It uses noticeably representative groups of nano-enabled products (NEPs) in the market (coatings and cosmetics), to formulate design hypothesis and to deliver safe and sustainable by design (SSbD) solutions by applying a data-driven approach and methodology. (Furxhi, et al., 2022) The methodology for designing new nano materials (NMs)/NEPs encompasses the merging of distinct data related to different scopes of the product, such as improved functionality (e.g., anti-aging capacity for cosmetics or photocatalytic activity for textiles), cost-effectiveness, environmental sustainability, and human and environmental safety.

Besides the experimental and scientific domain challenges of monitoring and denoting the properties' alterations and the effects of NMs/NEPs during their life cycle, the biggest challenge for data-driven reasoning is the FAIR capturing of the data from synthesis, incorporation, and use phase, to the end-of-life, in a transparent manner. (Furxhi, 2022) This challenge collecting multiple data sources from diverse domains requires the active involvement and constant participation, engagement, and collaboration of participants with different expertise.

The ASINA paradigm provided an opportunity to illustrate and report on the trials and ongoing development of capturing, communicating, and FAIRifying complex data from multidisciplinary sources.

The Data Shepherd of ASINA has conceptualized and initiated the design and implementation of the data FAIRification process with multiple stakeholders (i.e., data creators, data analysts and data re-users) who are unaccustomed with the notion of data management and FAIRification process, and is currently under development. (Furxhi, Arvanitis, Murphy, Costa, & Blosi, 2021) In ASINA, the extension of the newly defined Data Shepherd role oversees the lifecycle of the data rising from various fields, and simplifies, from their generation in a lab, to capturing into a worksheet and to FAIRification through the shepherd and external translation activities. The goal is the communication of information and knowledge across partners within a consortium.

Briefly, a questionnaire was prepared and circulated among relevant stakeholders to provide a first description of the data to be generated experimentally or simulated and the protocols and standards followed. The questionnaire allows communication between the partners involved in data generation and data shepherding. In addition, the protocols and standards followed are reported. The questionnaire allows parties involved in a specific life-cycle data generation phase and data shepherds to communicate and keep track of the data completeness. Once the questionnaire is completed by all parties, the Excel CEINT-NIKC²⁶ template with seven spreadsheet tabs, including tabs of publication, institution, people, measurement, protocol, instrument and dictionary, is selected for data and metadata capturing. A spreadsheet was selected due to its simplicity and familiarity to diverse users.

The NIKC template, is modified and adapted based on the experimentation and testing strategy, whereby descriptors of importance are selected together with the partners to reach project goals.

²⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/862444>; <https://www.asina-project.eu/>

²⁶ The CEINT NanoInformatics Knowledge Commons (NIKC) is a custom cyberinfrastructure consisting of a data repository and associated analytical tools developed to visualize and interrogate integrated datasets.

However, each project is a unique case study. ASINA's shepherd decided to construct case-specific templates that conceal aspects of the life-cycle and capture relevant metadata to make data intelligible. A template to insert data related to the functionality of NMs/NEPs, such as the antimicrobial properties, was created to fill the gap within the literature. (Furxhi, et al., 2021) In the latter article, the template allows flexible reporting of various functionality data, such as anti-aging or antioxidant capacities. Although safety is of primary importance within the nano-community, the performance of NMs/NEPs is paramount, because safe products that are not functional are not suitable for the market.

Antimicrobial data reported in a harmonized manner are scarce in the field of nanotechnology. The few literature reports of datasets are created manually with data extracted from the literature. (Mirzaei, Furxhi, Murphy, & Mullins, 2021) (Mirzaei, Furxhi, Murphy, & Mullins, 2021)

Next, a specific template for exposure field campaign monitoring data was developed and compared to existing ones. (Furxhi, et al., 2021) The paper demonstrates how different stakeholders communicate their needs within a consortium and with the shepherd, and reveals the need for specific goals within the project. For example, the raw data generated per second in the monitoring campaigns (Del Secco, et al., 2022) might be of lower value relative to a detailed overview of all data average. (Koivisto, et al., 2021) The templates work as a comprehensive worksheet for users to enter data on the materials being studied, experimental settings (instrumentation and protocols), and various outcomes of interest and their standard deviation produced for data-reuse purposes.

ASINA created a path for the onset of the data collection process, which is based on non-technical scientific FAIR principles that supplement the original principles and outlines the procedures involved by data creators without overcomplicating the concept. (Furxhi, Arvanitis, Murphy, Costa, & Blosi, 2021) The ad hoc collaboration between stakeholders and the shepherd allowed the generation of a consensus template and is crucial to the reliability, quality and application of the data generation and capturing strategy. From a data shepherd perspective, the most challenging part was to leap from the outlined information of the questionnaire to the comprehensive state of a filled-in ready-to-use data template. A key finding is that the process is iterative until a consensus is reached between the data creators and other partners.

In terms of the challenges of FAIRification, many research organisations lack the necessary expertise, and many researchers view the process as additional "administration" work that does not directly progress their work. It can be challenging for researchers who are inexperienced with the concept of data management to implement these principles.

Metadata capturing is not frequently promoted in regular academic practice, despite its importance. This is due to a lack of data management training and a prevalent perception of data management as something that happens after data has been thoroughly evaluated and published. Successful data management necessitates a change in the research culture, to move an organization from a protective data mentality to a mindset of data sharing and exploitation with all relevant stakeholders. Such a change in successful data management obliges a shift in research culture. Data Shepherds, who sit at the epicentre of the data lifecycle, simplify the interaction between stakeholders, and ensure the value of FAIR data is recognised, can accelerate this change.

The Shepherd's task cannot be fulfilled without the cooperation of all partners. In some circumstances, responsible data shepherding demands perseverance and an ability to engage top-level management and provide technical collaboration at the project's core with hands-on expertise.

External assistance from TA services can facilitate and speed up the curation process. Until data FAIRification methods and culture are established, such projects should be fostered. Further consultations will be unnecessary after a critical mass of FAIRification implementations has been reached and training saturation has been achieved. The ASINA instances provide the scientific community with practical information about data shepherding; because this is a relatively young profession, such extensive work aids in its development.

13. Appendix B – List of Text Books

Alexopolous, P. (2020) Semantic Modeling for Data: Avoiding Pitfalls and Breaking Dilemmas. Sebastopol CA, USA: O'Reilly

Allemang, D. & Hendler, J. (2011) Semantic Web for the Working Ontologist. (2nd ed.) Burlington USA: Morgan Kaufmann Publishers.

Hedden, H. (2022). The accidental taxonomist (3rd ed.) Medford NJ, USA: Information Today, Inc.

Hitzler, P.; Krötzsch, M. and Rudolph, S. (2009) Foundations of Semantic Web Technologies. London, UK: Chapman & Hall.

Horgan, A.; Blomqvist, E.; Cochez, M.; d'Amato, C. & de Melo, G. (2021) Knowledge Graphs. San Rafael CA, USA: Morgan & Claypool Publishers.

Hogan, A.; Blomqvist, E.; Cochez, M.; d'Amato C., de Melo, G.; Gutierrez, C.; Kirrane, S.; Labra Gayo, J. E.; Navigli, R.; Neumaier, S.; Ngonga Ngomo A.-C.; Polleres, A.; Rashid, S. M.; Rula, A.; Schmelzeisen, L.; Sequeda, J.; Staab, S. & Zimmermann A. (2021) Knowledge Graphs, Synthesis Lectures on Data, Semantics, and Knowledge, No. 22, 1–237, Cham, Switzerland: Springer.

Lippell, H. (2022). Taxonomies: Practical Approaches to Developing and Manging Vocabularies for Digital Information. London, UK: Facet Publishing.

14. Appendix C – List of Blogs, Whitepapers, and Reports

Cambridge Semantics; <https://cambridgesemantics.com/category/blog/>

Harmse, Henriette; <https://henrietteharmse.com>

Mungall, Chris; <https://douroucouli.wordpress.com/author/cmungall/>

Ontotext; https://www.ontotext.com/knowledge-hub/white_paper/,
<https://www.ontotext.com/knowledge-hub/publications/>

SciBite; <https://scibite.com/news/>

Stardog; <https://www.stardog.com/resources/>

15. Appendix D – List of MOOCs and Online Training

CambridgeSemantics - <https://cambridgesemantics.com/blog/semantic-university/>

Their goal is to make it easy for anyone to get started with semantic web technologies and methodologies.

EIT Digital Professional School - <https://professionalschool.eitdigital.eu/>

Offers short courses for professionals on various topics related to digital technology and innovation.

FAIRCOOKBOOK - <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/content/search-wizard.html>

This offers a collection of annotated workflows.

FutureLearn- <https://www.futurelearn.com/subjects/science-engineering-and-maths-courses/data-science>

They offer courses around data science often provided by universities.

LOT - <https://lot.linkeddata.es/#stories>

LOT (Linked Open Terms) Methodology is an industrial method for developing ontologies and vocabularies.

MIRIADAX - <https://miriadax.net/curso/mastering-ontology-development-a-practical-approach-4th-edition/>

An online learning platform offering free and low-cost courses in Spanish.

openHPI – <https://open.hpi.de/courses>

An open and free digital education platform for lifelong learners, professionals, university and school students. Course topics are e.g., Big Data and AI, Cybersecurity, Internet and Programming.

Ontotext - <https://www.ontotext.com/knowledge-hub/fundamentals/>

Offers information on fundamentals, such as Knowledge Graph, SPARQL, etc.

PoolParty Academy - <https://www.poolparty.biz/academy>

Offers detailed information about knowledge graphs

Protégé - https://protegewiki.stanford.edu/wiki/Main_Page

A free, open-source platform that provides a suite of tools to construct domain models and knowledge-based applications with ontologies.